

Chemical Studies on *Ailanthus excelsa*

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- 2
 a, A = morpholino
 b, A = piperidino
 c, A = anilino
 d, A = 4-Cl-anilino
 e, A = 4-Br-anilino
 f, A = 4-CH₃-anilino
 g, A = 4-OCH₃-anilino
 h, A = 4-NO₂-anilino
 i, A = 4-COOH-anilino
 j, A = 4-COOH₂-anilino
 k, A = 4-COOC₂H₅-anilino
 l, A = 4-(N-morpholino)anilino
 m, A = 4-(N-piperidino)anilino
 n, A = 4-(N-morpholinocarbonyl)anilino
 o, A = 4-(N-piperidinocarbonyl)anilino

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TABLE 1

Carbon number	Glucarubin (DMSO-d ₆)	Excelsin (DMSO-d ₆)
1	82.6	82.6 (d)
2	71.3	71.3 (d)
3	125.7	125.8 (d)
4	133.8	133.8 (s)
5	40.1	40.1 (d)
6	24.9	24.8 (t)
7	77.9	77.9 (d)
8	46.7	46.8 (s)
9	40.9	41.0 (d)
10	44.1 ^a	44.2 (s)
11	109.1	109.2 (s)
12	78.5	78.4 (d)
13	31.4	31.4 (d)
14	44.6 ^a	44.4 (d)
15	69.5	68.9 (d)
16	167.1	167.4 (s)
17	70.1	70.2 (t)
18	14.8	14.6 (q)
19	10.1	9.7 (q)
20	20.9	20.8 (q)
Side Chain		
1'	170.4	170.3 (s)
2'	73.9	39.5 (d)
3'	32.6	26.2 (t)
4'	7.7	11.1 (q)
5'	24.9	15.8 (q)

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7-H, vicinal to lactone), 3.16 (1H, s, 9H), 1.69 (3H, s, 10-CH₃), 4.05 (1H, d, 3H z, 12H), 1.39 (3H, d, 13-CH₃), 6.14 (1H, d, 11Hz, 15-H, vicinal to ester function), 4.19 and 3.62 (each 1H, d, 8.5Hz, 17 CH₂-O, hemiketal), 1.22 (3H, d, 2'-CH₃) and 1.07 (3H, t, CH₃CH₂). Although molecular ion peak is reported² for this compound but no such peak was discernible in the spectrum of the compound isolated by us. On the contrary mass fragment ions appear at *m/e* 462, C₂₈H₃₄O₈ (M⁺-H₂O); 361, C₂₀H₂₅O₆ (462-101 mass units of the C₈ acid side chain); 360, C₂₀H₂₄O₆; 231, C₁₄H₁₈O₈; 85, C₄H₆O; 57, C₄H₆ (base peak).

The ¹³C nmr spectrum of excelsin is very similar to that of glaucarubin³ from which it differs only in the nature of the side chain. The chemical shifts of glaucarubin and the chemical shift and multiplicities (obtained from the Sford spectra and denoted in parenthesis) of excelsin are depicted in Table 1.

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Quercetin-3-O-β-D-galactopyranosyl(1→4)-O-α-L-rhamnopyranoside from Root of *Anogeissus latifolia* Wall.

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ANOGEISSUS latifolia Wall. (N.O. Comberataceae) is a medicinal plant^{1,2} which is distributed throughout the greater part of India. Because of its great medicinal importance, its phytochemical investigation was undertaken.

Experimental

The roots of *Anogeissus latifolia* Wall. (4 kg) collected from the forest of Patharia Hills, Sagar (authenticated by the Department of Botany of this University) were powdered and extracted with light petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°). The defatted roots were extracted with 95% ethanol, and the ethanol extract concentrated under reduced pressure to a brown viscous mass was resolved into water-soluble and water-insoluble parts. The water-soluble part was concentrated and successively extracted with benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate and acetone. The chloroform-soluble part gave the glycoside which was purified by passing over a column of silica gel G and crystallised as yellow needles

with petrol-benzene, m.p. 272-74°. The homogeneity of the glycoside was checked by paper chromatography in n-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5), R_f 0.34, yield 0.052%.

Results and Discussion

The glycoside, m.p. 272-74°, showed positive Shinoda test for flavonoid. Hydrolysis of the glycoside with ethanolic sulphuric acid (7%) afforded an aglycone and the sugars identified as D-galactose and L-rhamnose (by co-pc, co-tlc).

The aglycone crystallised from petrol-chloroform as pale yellow crystals, m.p. 212-14° (Found : C, 59.62; H, 3.31. C₁₅H₁₀O₇ requires C, 59.60; H, 3.33%). The structure to the aglycone was assigned as 3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxy flavone (quercetin) by m.m.p., degradative studies and spectral analysis and is a well known compound.

The hydrolysability of the glycoside with almond emulsion³ yielding D-galactose, the first appearance of D-galactose on partial hydrolysis (1% H₂SO₄), consumption of 3.02 mole of periodate⁴ with the production of 1.3 mole of formic acid per mole of the glycoside; acid hydrolysis of the permethylated glycoside⁵ (DMS/dry K₂CO₃ yielding 2,3-di-O-methyl-α-L-rhamnose and 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-β-D-galactose (by co-pc and co-tlc) indicated the sugar moiety to be β-D-galactopyranosyl(1→4)-O-α-L-rhamnopyranoside attached to C-3-free OH group present in the aglycone. Attachment of sugar residue at C-3 was further supported by uv shift. The aglycone as well as the glycoside showed the presence of free OH groups at C-3' and C-4' (uv shift upon addition of AlCl₃/H₃BO₃)⁶, at C-5 and C-7 (uv shift with AlCl₃ and CH₃COONa)⁷, while C-3 OH was present in the aglycone (yellow fluorescence in uv light)⁸ and absence in the glycoside (no yellow fluorescence), thus confirming the structure of the glycoside as quercetin-3-O-β-D-galactopyranosyl(1→4)-O-α-L-rhamnopyranoside, further supported by nmr spectrum, δ 7.35 (d, 2.5 H_z, H-2'), 7.65 (dd, 2.5 and 9H_z, H-6), 7.0 (d, 9H_z, H-5'), 6.50 (d, 2.4 H_z, H-6), 6.53 (d, 2H_z, H-8), 5.47 (d, 2H_z, 1' H, anomeric proton of rhamnose), 0.78 (d, 6H_z, methyl group of rhamnose), 4.9 (d, 7H_z, 1'' H, anomeric proton of galactose), 3.5-3.7 (m, 6 protons of galactosyl unit) 2.35-2.49 (s, 4×OAc aromatic and 2.09-2.21 (6×OAc sugar acyl group).

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